

USING UZBEK WORD-FORMATION MODELS IN THE NATIONALIZATION OF FOREIGN WORDS

Khamrayev Fozilbek Yuldoshevish

Doctoral student of Karshi State University (Karshi, Uzbekistan)

Xamrayev-fozil@mail.ru

Abstract

This article discusses the importance of Uzbek word formation models in naming new concepts in the language, as well as in the nationalization of foreign words. In it, it is justified through examples that there are five main methods of forming words (terms) in the Uzbek language within the noun group, and it is also emphasized that the activation of the abbreviation method in the Uzbek language is the need of the hour.

Key words: word formation models, nationalization, term, semantic method, affixation, composition, syntactic method, abbreviation.

As the changes in the life of the society are expressed in the language, due to the need to name new concepts, the existing models of word formation are being improved according to the needs of the times. The Uzbek language has its own new word formation models that have been formed historically. However, recently, the increasing influence of foreign words on the Uzbek language has a negative impact on the possibilities of creating a national name. Accordingly, careful study and improvement of word formation models of the Uzbek language, effective use of them in the nationalization of foreign words is one of the urgent issues of modern Uzbek linguistics.

The main part of new words in modern Uzbek language, including borrowed words, is made up of lexical units belonging to the noun family. In this case, taking into account this aspect and the overall scope of the work, only artificial words belonging to the noun family were analyzed.

From today's point of view, the following types of formation of new words (nouns) are distinguished:

Semantic (lexical semantic) method. This method is considered in some sources as a historical (diachronic) method [1: 171; 2: 5]. However, the analysis of new words (neologisms) belonging to different fields shows that the semantic method is still

active and plays an important role in filling new lexical gaps that have appeared in the language.

N. Mahmudov paid special attention to this process [3; 120]. Word formation by using existing words in a new sense is often observed, especially within terms. G. Ismailov's candidate's dissertation is dedicated to this issue, in which the semantic method in the formation of field terms, i.e., the specific role of transterminization, is researched for the first time in a monographic plan, the existence of specific patterns of transterminization identified, and the role of transterms in the formation of doublets, variants, and homonymy was reassessed [4; 27].

The word *page* generally means "each side of a page of a book, notebook, etc.", in the field of information technology, it is a term that means "a document with a unique address that can be opened and viewed using a viewing program". Or if the word *signature* generally means "a sign expressed by a person in a special writing-drawing (form) by his own hand and confirming that he is himself", in the field of information technology means "small text containing surname, first name, address and other information" [5; 85, 208]. In addition, it can be found among the new onomastic units.

Method of Affixation. Affixation is undoubtedly the most productive method of word formation in the Uzbek language. After gaining independence, the following affixes are effectively used to form words (nouns) through affixes in the Uzbek language.

Suffix *-ma*. It forms nouns with different meanings from additional verbs, and in rare cases from other categories. For example, *sinama* (instead of Russian *проба*) is a medical term; injecting a very small amount of a powerful drug (antibiotic) into the body as a test to determine whether it has a negative effect on the body.

It is also creating nouns from its own bases to express modern concepts within the terms of various fields. In particular, the word *kodlama* (proportion between symbols (human language) and numbers (computer language)) is one of the new terms related to computer technology, created as an Uzbek alternative to the English words *encoding*, Russian *кодировка* [5; 111].

Suffix *-gich*. This suffix is also added to verbs to form a noun denoting what is intended to perform the action understood from this verb: such as *ushlagich*, *yutgich*, *ko'rsatgich*, *quritgich*, *bug'lagich*, *hisoblagich*, *kuchaytirgich*, *ta'minlagich*, *tozalagich*.

Composition method. The majority of artificial words in the lexicon of the Uzbek language are words made by adding words to words, that is, by the method of

composition, and this method is still widely used today. According to their content, they can be divided into two groups:

1) compound words created on the basis of an internal source (here, the Arabic and Persian words, which are completely absorbed into the Uzbek language, are also considered as internal sources);

2) compound words, part of which is formed on the basis of an external source.

The main part of compound words created on the basis of an internal source is made up of social and household spheres: such as *yurtboshi*, *hamjamiyat*, *hamdo'stlik*, *asabbuzarlik*, *baliqtozalagich*, *boshqotirma*, *tishkovlagich*, *umume'tirof*, *umumjahon*, *umumta'lim*, *gulqog'oz*, *qo'lband*, *tizzaband*, *orttasvir*, *yo'lchiroq*, *otashkesim*.

O. Shukurov, taking into account that the concept of "confirmation of a person" is at the root of the term *autentifikatsiya*, he believes that it can be nationalized in the form of *tasdiqshaxs* in the sense of a person to be confirmed [6; 83]. One can fully agree with this opinion. Because the word *autentifikatsiya* is phonetically and graphically not adapted to the Uzbek language, it is very difficult to remember its meaning. The word *tasdiqshaxs* is easy to pronounce and concise, and you can easily imagine what it means.

Compound words, part of which is made up of a foreign language element, can be grouped based on several patterns:

1) *audio* + own word (*audiodarslik*, *audiokitob*, *audiomatn*);

2) *avia* + own word (*aviahalokat*, *aviakorxonona*, *aviatashuv*, *aviaqatnov*);

3) *avto* + own word (*avtobekat*, *avtomaktab*, *avtoturargoh*, *avtoxo'jalik*, *avtoyuklagich*);

4) *kiber* + own word (*kiberhujum*, *kiberjinoiyat*, *kiberkasallik*, *kibermadaniyat*, *kibermakon*, *kiberxavfsizlik*);

5) *video* + own word (*videodars*, *videokuzatuv*, *videokuchaytirgich*, *videoanjuman*, *videomuloqot*).

Syntactic method. When it is not possible to name a new concept in the language with one word, it should be expressed syntactically, that is, through a unit equivalent to a word combination. Although they are not interpreted as artificial words in linguistics, they make up a significant part of the fund of terms belonging to various fields. It follows that compound nouns have essentially the status of terms, which differ from simple word combinations whose parts can be freely replaced. In general, it is more correct to approach such units as a separate lexical unit, a separate way of creating new names (terms).

In the article of A.Teshaboyev and A.Nurmonov on the issues of standardization of terms of exact and natural sciences, the problem of compound term(s) was specifically addressed. It is noted that terms are divided into simple and compound (consisting of two or more words) types according to their composition [7; 72-76].

H. Dadaboyev admits that Uzbek terminology is enriched by a large number of term-combinations in the present period, and he divides them into several types from the point of view of content, i.e. two-component, three-component, four-component, five and more divides into content term-combinations [8; 91]. But observations show that the majority of such units are two-component (two-word) term-combinations.

Abbreviation method. Shortening words (abbreviation method) is one of the modern methods of creating a new name (term). Abbreviations entered the Uzbek language through the Russian language [1; 186] and are found only within the noun group.

In the Uzbek language, the scope of word formation in this way is quite limited, that is, they are mainly used to name local and international organizations, enterprises and associations: such as *SHHT* (*Shanxay hamkorlik tashkiloti*), *OTM* (*Oliy ta'lim muassasasi*), *O'zJOKU* (*O'zbekiston jurnalistika va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar universiteti*), *OAV* (*Ommaviy axborot vositalari*), *MIB* (*Majburiy ijro byurosi*), *MFY* (*Mahalla fuqarolar yig'ini*), *O'zgidromet* (*O'zbekiston Respublikasi gidrometeorologiya xizmati markazi*).

Implementation of this method on a wider scale, in particular, active use of it in the creation of related nouns (object, place, activity process) will undoubtedly fill a certain part of the need for new national creations. Currently, in English, one of the most influential languages in the world, the abbreviation method has become one of the main types of creating new names, and it has several forms [9; 5-10]. Currently, English words such as *radar*, *laser*, *PR*, *email*, *modem*, *blog*, *wi-fi*, which are actively used in the Uzbek language, are also products of the shortening method.

There are many such examples in modern English. Proper and effective use of abbreviations of various forms in the Uzbek language is important in ensuring nationalism, as well as in alleviating to a certain extent the pressure of foreign languages.

So, the Uzbek language has its own new word formation models that have been formed over the centuries. From the point of view of the modern era, they can be grouped within the noun family as follows: 1) words formed by semantic method; 2) words formed by the method of affixation; 3) words formed by the method of composition (adding words to words); 4) syntactically formed words; 5) words

formed by shortening (abbreviation). The role of these models in creating new words (terms) is not the same. That is, when it is not possible to use the main methods (models) (semantics, affixation, composition), it is appropriate to rely on names equal to the compound or reduction methods. In general, in-depth study of the possibilities of creating new words of the Uzbek language and their full use are important in ensuring the balance of foreign words and nationalized words.

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